

The effect of particle size on thermal insulation performance of eco-friendly waste fibers

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Thermal insulation is a vital necessity in the current world context due to high energy costs and demand. Conventional heat insulation materials cause adverse health risks. Therefore, material scientists and engineers have focused on finding biodegradable alternatives. This study investigates the thermal performance of eco-friendly waste materials including cocopeat, rice husks, rice straws, and chicken feathers. Experiments were conducted on materials with particle sizes of 0.5 mm, 2 mm, 4 mm, and 6 mm, separated using aluminum meshes. Samples were prepared with a thickness of 8.5 ± 0.5 mm and a density 0.4991 ± 0.016 g/cm³. Thermal conductivity was measured using the Lees' disc method, and moisture absorption tests were conducted for all samples. The best thermal performance was obtained by selecting samples while comparing the lowest moisture absorption and highest thermal resistivity. The results showed that the best-performing particle sizes were 0.5 mm for rice straws (moisture absorption: 9.09% / 24 hours, thermal conductivity coefficient: 0.30 W/mK), 4 mm for cocopeat (moisture absorption: 3.70% / 24 hours, thermal conductivity coefficient: 0.33 W/mK), 2 mm for rice husks (moisture absorption: 10.77% / 24 hours, thermal conductivity coefficient: 0.31 W/mK), and 2 mm for chicken feathers (moisture absorption: 4.81% / 24 hours, thermal conductivity coefficient: 0.37 W/mK). These findings highlight the potential of using eco-friendly waste materials for thermal insulation applications. Further, it helps to preserve the environment and save energy.

Keywords: *Insulation materials, Thermal conductivity coefficient, Nature-Based, Building materials*